

Polymer Composites

TUHH
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CAPACITANCE MEASUREMENTS ON INTEGRATED CARBON FIBRE ROVINGS FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING IN GFRP

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Electrical SHM method for detection and evaluation of damages in GFRP

Local fibre replacement

- Fully-integrated, conductive carbon fibre bundles
→ Capacitance measurements for damage sensing

Manufacturing Bundle Specimens

Bundle Replacement

- Gurit non-crimp E-glass fabric UT-E250
- CF rovings FT300B 6000-50B

RTM-Process

- Epoxy system: Hexion RIMR 135 & RIMH 137
- Heat press 16 h @ 50 °C
- Post-curing 16 h @ 80 °C

Specimen Preparation

- Cutting using a precision saw
- Contacting using silver conductive paint

Specimen Geometries including CF Bundles

Capacitance-based Sensing

DIN EN ISO 527-4

[0/90₄]_s

15 mm

- Correlation of capacitance decrease and crack evolution
- Sensitivity sufficient → CF bundles suitable, material-conform electrodes

More information:
[Bug2021]

Analytical Modelling

DIN EN ISO 527-4

[0/90₄]_s

15 mm

- Analytical modelling confirms cracks as main effect for capacitance decrease
- Assumptions regarding air as second medium and rectangular cracks sufficient

More information:
[Bug2021]

Capacitance-based Sensing

DIN EN ISO 527-4

$[90_2/0/45_2]_s$
 $[90_2/0/45_2]_s$

- Suitable bundle configurations allow detection of damages in different composite layers

More information:
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Detection of Impacts

[0/90₄]_s

30 mm

GFRP

GFRP Air

Air

GFRP

- Detection and size estimation of impact damages via capacitance decrease
- Smart sensor layout and contacting enables damage localisation

More information:
[Bug2022b]

Fully-integrated, conductive carbon fibre bundles for damage sensing in GFRP

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- No significant reduction of strength and modulus
 - Detection of matrix cracks and impact damages via capacitance decrease
 - Suitable sensor design and contacting enables damage localisation

Thank you for your attention!

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C. Buggisch, A. Gagani, and B. Fiedler. (2021). Capacitance measurements on integrated conductors for detection of matrix cracks in GFRP. *Functional Composite Materials*. **2**, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42252-020-00013-x>

[Bug2022]

C. Buggisch. (2022). Structurally compatible embedded sensors for damage detection in glass fibre reinforced polymers. *Technisch-wissenschaftliche Schriftenreihe/ TUHH Polymer Composites*. **42**, <https://doi.org/10.15480/882.4557>

[Bug2022b]

C. Buggisch, D. Gibhardt, M. Kern, and B. Fiedler. (2022). Impact damage detection in glass fibre reinforced polymers via electrical capacitance measurements on integrated carbon fibre bundles. *Composites Communications*. **30**, 101090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2022.101090>